

FORMATION OF UNIVERSAL COMPETENCIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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In the world's leading higher education organizations, innovative models of improving the content of education are being put into practice to clarify the scientific aspects of the development of research activities of educators, increase their level of professional training. The concept of international education until 2030, adopted by the UNESCO Organization, defines "having a solid foundation of knowledge, developing creative and critical thinking, research activities" as an urgent task. In the activities of conducting research, it is advisable to form, improve students' comprehensive competencies, effectively organize their knowledge, skills, research and cognitive and reflexive activities. Systematic work is being carried out to identify the problem in the educational process and improve the individual educational trajectory of students based on the effective use of experiments, teaching technologies aimed at the formation of universal competence, heuristic activities, small research and creative project formation.

In the world educational and scientific research tasks, scientific research is carried out to prepare pedagogical personnel for professional activities, to increase the quality of education to an international level, to further increase the Universal competencies of students in educational classes, to independently analyze them in cognitive, analytical, creative thinking, Information and phenomena, to follow the research culture, to master analysis and synthesis, to

In our republic, in recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on the cognitive potential of the pedagogical staff in the introduction of modern educational methods, adaptation of lessons to the requirements of the time, raising students' knowledge. It is necessary that each pedagogical cadre be a mature cadre whose work on it can meet the requirements of the Times. "Today, every teacher and educator, the domla of the High School, who can apply the latest positive innovations in education and science to educational processes, should become the owner of deep knowledge and worldview, in a word, the most advanced representatives of our time and society." In elementary education, the methodology for the formation of universal competence and the possibilities of improving va technology will expand in educational classes.

Today, special attention is paid to improving the quality of education and the development of Science and education in our country. The development of primary education is an integral part of Education. The increase in attention to education is of particular importance not only in our country, but also in the world. Currently, there is an increasing amount of scientific research on the development of students' competencies on base and science, improving the methodology for harmonizing the content of education with the achievements of Science, International Programs for assessing the level of student assimilation and diagnosing the formation of student competencies.

The concept of development of the public education system in our republic was approved until 2030, five initiatives were put into practice, which included comprehensive measures aimed at creating additional conditions for youth education, state educational standards and science curricula based on a competency approach to general secondary education were developed, normative foundations of participation in international studies for assessing the quality of education were created. In the new Uzbekistan development strategy for 2022-2026, the fourth priority will be on the issues of "conducting a fair social policy, developing human capital", which will pay special attention to "improving the quality of education in schools, bringing the knowledge and skills of pedagogical staff to an international level." Increasing the quality of education the emphasis is placed on bringing education to the international level. This expands the possibilities of providing the educational process with the necessary information, finding and introducing optimal solutions to their assimilation. Today's modern education requires that not only teaching, but also nurturing, beyond it, the formation of competencies, teaching young people to think creatively, independently. Including competency, let us give a definition to the concepts of competence.

The concepts of "competence" and "competence" entered the theory and practice of professional training of those educated in higher education institutions from the late 1960s to the early 1970s. At the symposium on the program of the Council of Europe in Bern (1996), it was noted that the concept of "competence" is included among such concepts as "training", "competence", "competence", "competence". At the symposium on the program of the Council of Europe in Bern (1996), it was noted that the concept of "competence" is included among such concepts as "training", "competence", "competence", "competence".

Competence (lot. *Competo* I achieve, I deserve, I deserve) means knowledge, experience in one area or another. Competence is said to instill knowledge, professional suitability, competence, responsibility in the activities of the leader. That is, the perfect knowledge of the secrets of his field in every possible way, and the true owner of his profession. So it can be seen from this that we also agree with the opinions of supporters of the school of development of moral sciences of management schools. That is, in competence we can see exactly the existence of psychological categories of a person.

It should be noted that the concept of “competence” in modern science is controversial because it is not clearly interpreted in the form of a legal definition enshrined in legal documents in education. A.V.Khutorsky and G.K.Selevko's approaches cite the concept of competence and its difference from other related concepts. A.V.Khutorsky explains that competence, reflecting the social prospects of society from the result of educational upbringing, is a predetermined, special regulatory requirement for the result of the educational process, which is necessary for the effective professional activity of the listener in a certain area in the future. G.K.Selevko explains that competence allows us to take into account the subjective position of the educational process, effectively identify and organize internal and external resources to achieve a professionally important or other goal .

Accordingly, we take educational competencies according to the definition given in the approved standard:

- knowledge-remembering and re-explaining learned information;
- skill-ability to apply learned knowledge in familiar situations;
- competence — to be able to apply learned knowledge and formed skills in unfamiliar situations and to generate new knowledge;

* competence — the ability to apply existing knowledge, skills and qualifications in everyday activities.

In the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, such tasks as qualitatively updating the content of the continuing education system, improving the teaching methodology, focusing on the in - depth study of basic subjects, developing criteria for assessing pedagogical activity based on competencies provided for by state educational standards are established. There are several types of competence, within which Universal competence is also distinguished. The formation of universal competence is the formation of students in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland, kindness to people, adherence to Universal and

national values, knowledge of values of universal importance (customs, rituals, national – cultural traditions), respect for him, respect for other people, formation of universal competence in the spirit of respect for benevolent, authentic, national and ethnic characteristics. Each discipline provides an opportunity for the formation of competencies in students through its own function, which follows from this.

Therefore, today it is necessary to form students with modern, sought-after and professional competence in the educational system of our country, who can meet the requirements of the time, and to form qualified personnel in the lessons so that even your pedagogical staff can meet the requirements of the time today

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